

ERA-NET Cofund on Blue Bioeconomy (BlueBio) – Unlocking the Potential of Aquatic Bioresources

SMARTCHAIN

Smart solutions for advancing supply systems
in blue bioeconomy value chains

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Initial draft of indicators selected for stakeholder engagement and consultation

SmartChain
Blue Bioeconomy Solutions

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

SMARTCHAIN focuses on circular economy solutions for the blue bioeconomy. The bioeconomy “is the production of renewable biological resources and the conversion of these resources and waste streams into value added products, such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy” (COM, 2019, p. 8). The blue bioeconomy emphasizes aquatic or marine environments, and involves a specific focus on novel applications, including non-food, food, and feed. The blue bioeconomy includes both primary and secondary activities and other sectors (tertiary) may be connected to the blue bioeconomy through their services to bioeconomic activities (Nordic Council, 2014). A transition towards a circular economy for the blue bioeconomy can contribute to resource efficiency gains which are integral to sustainable development. This task selected a set of indicators for sustainability assessments based on a review of existing indicators with a focus on the circularity approach for the selected SMARTCHAIN case studies.

OBJECTIVES

The purpose of task 3.1 is to provide a set of sustainability indicators that can be used to assess blue bioeconomy activities in general and more specifically for the fisheries and aquaculture sectors which are the primary focus of the SmartChain project.

KEY FINDINGS

The framework selected was the Blue Economy Sustainability Framework which was further cross-referenced with the FAO’s sustainable bioeconomy indicators and the GRI standards. Two company sustainability reports were also examined to see what is being currently reported on in practice as a first indication of data availability. The final selection resulted in 35 indicators in the environmental dimension, 14 indicators in the economic dimension, 21 indicators in the social dimension and 20 indicators in the governance dimension (Section 3). These comprise the core set. The supplementary sets, harvesting fish and shellfish, processing fish and shellfish and aquaculture include an additional 11 for harvesting, 22 for processing and 19 for aquaculture respectively (listed in Annex I).

NEXT STEPS

Defining thresholds either through targets based on national-level policy targets or sectoral level targets (where available) using trend-based assessment where well-defined thresholds are not available. Further discussion at the project level is also necessary to define those indicators most specific to the aims of other WPs. Ongoing work includes multistakeholder interviews/focus groups covering the sustainability dimensions and probing further on circularity and governance more broadly.

1 INTRODUCTION

As part of the Green Deal, the European Commission has adopted a new Circular Economy Action Plan to promote circular economy processes, sustainable consumption, and more efficient use of resources (COM, 2020). The circular economy paradigm calls for the redesign of the linear economic system whereby the environmental and social costs of products are externalized, to a circular system based on closed-loop resource flows that can preserve the embedded environmental and economic value in products over time. It is a way to increase resource efficiency by intentionally narrowing, slowing, and closing materials and energy flows (Pieroni et al, 2019).

SMARTCHAIN focuses on circular economy solutions for the blue bioeconomy. The bioeconomy “is the production of renewable biological resources and the conversion of these resources and waste streams into value added products, such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy” (COM, 2019, p. 8). The blue bioeconomy emphasizes aquatic or marine environments, and involves a specific focus on novel applications, including non-food, food, and feed. The blue bioeconomy includes both primary and secondary activities and other sectors may be connected to the blue bioeconomy through their services to bioeconomic activities (Nordic Council, 2014).

A transition towards a circular economy for the blue bioeconomy can contribute to resource efficiency gains which are integral to sustainable development. The blue bioeconomy needs to follow the principles of sustainable development such that it contributes to meeting the needs of present generations without compromising the needs of future generations through a focus on the three main pillars of sustainability: economic, social, and environmental (Fritsche et al., 2020). Blue bioeconomy development can support the achievement of broad societal goals such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through an emphasis on sustainability, circularity, and innovative approaches (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 The overlapping concepts of Bioeconomy and Circular Economy (Adapted from: Carus & Dammer, 2018).

The purpose of task 3.1 is to provide a set of sustainability indicators that can be used to assess blue bioeconomy activities in general and more specifically for the fisheries and aquaculture sectors which are the primary focus of the SmartChain project. To avoid duplication of efforts (Bracco et al., 2019), the sustainability indicators were selected from pre-existing frameworks relevant to the topic of circular blue bioeconomy. Two frameworks were

selected as most relevant to the aims of task 3.1: the FAO's "Indicators to monitor and evaluate the sustainability of bioeconomy" (Bracco et al., 2019) and the European Commission's "Sustainability criteria for the blue economy" (COM, 2021). In addition, the GRI standards and two company reports were examined to gauge which sort of data companies are reporting on in practice.

In what follows, a brief overview of the use of indicators in assessments and of the two indicator frameworks is provided, then the methods (Section 2) and results i.e., the selected indicators (Section 3) are presented and finally the conclusion and next steps (Section 4).

SUSTAINABILITY INDICATORS

Sustainability indicators are an assessment tool for measuring performance towards specific goals which it is hoped will bring us towards a more sustainable state (Hák, Moldan & Dahl, 2007). An indicator set is a group of indicators organized together for a specific purpose, in this case a sustainable blue bioeconomy. A dashboard of indicators is a collection of indicators often organized by themes (e.g., sustainability pillars) but not prioritized, weighed, or aggregated. An index is a set of indicators which have been weighed and aggregated to provide a single score. This process does provide simplicity in interpretation but can obscure the underlying issues especially when the normalization, weighing and aggregation procedures are too arbitrary (Böhringer & Jochem, 2007). A dashboard of indicators can, however, include both single indicators and indices. Practice based indicators and standards are also often included in indicator sets. The unit for those indicators is then a yes/no answer to whether a certain policy or practice has been implemented. Those can further be quantitatively calculated as dummy indicators which can take two values, 0 (no) and 1 (yes) (Bracco et al., 2019). These are often used where other data is not available or not easily quantified. Other commonly used types of indicators are footprint-type indicators such as material, carbon, water, and land and adjusted economic indicators. Footprint-type indicators are aggregated indicators based on scientifically defined methodologies which measure the environmental sustainability of production and consumption. (Bracco et al., 2019). Adjusted economic indicators are often used to measure the decoupling of environmental pressures from economic growth e.g., waste generation compared to GDP growth. In this example, when waste generation is reduced while GDP grows it is referred to as "absolute decoupling", When waste generation remains steady while GDP grows it is referred to as "relative decoupling" (Ruffing, 2007). Relative decoupling is a desired state, but absolute decoupling is considered necessary to achieve sustainability as biophysical limits have to be taken into account (Vadén et al., 2020).

INDICATOR FRAMEWORKS

The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)'s approach builds on a set of aspirational principles and criteria (see Table 1.) which provide the wider scope and aims for the identified indicators. The indicators were further selected through the review of pre-existing frameworks, including standards such as the Marine Stewardship Council (MSC) and the Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC), to avoid duplication of efforts. Two approaches of monitoring and evaluation were delineated: the territorial approach ranging from global, regional, national, and subnational levels and the product/value chain approach. In addition, integral sectors to the bioeconomy were also identified and indicators selected specific to each of those sectors where relevant and appropriate (Bracco et al., 2019). Sectors range from primary and secondary production to tertiary sectors that cover consumption and end-of-life options.

Table 1 FAO's Aspirational Principles and Criteria for the Bioeconomy (adapted from FAO, 2021).

Sustainability dimension	Principles	Criteria	Connection to the SDGs
Society	1. Sustainable bioeconomy development should support food security and nutrition at all levels	1.1 Food security and nutrition are supported	SDGs 2 & 3
		1.2 Sustainable intensification of biomass production is promoted	
		1.3 Adequate land rights and rights to other natural resources are guaranteed	
		1.4 Food safety, disease prevention and human health are ensured	
Environment	2. Sustainable bioeconomy ensure that natural resources are conserved, protected and enhanced	2.1 Biodiversity conservation is ensured	SDGs 14 & 15
		2.2 Climate change mitigation and adaptation are pursued	
		2.3 Water quality and quantity are maintained, and, as much as possible, enhanced	
		2.4 The degradation of land, soil, forests and marine environments is prevented, stopped or reversed	
Economy	3. Sustainable bioeconomy should support competitive and inclusive economic growth	3.1 Economic development is fostered	SDGs 5, 7 & 8
		3.2 Inclusive economic growth is strengthened	
		3.3 Resilience of the rural and urban economy is enhanced	
Society	4. Sustainable bioeconomy should make communities healthier, more sustainable, and harness social and ecosystem resilience	4.1 The sustainability of urban centres is enhanced	SDGs 1 & 11
		4.2 Resilience of biomass producers, rural communities and ecosystems is developed and/or strengthened	
Environment	5. Sustainable bioeconomy should rely on improved efficiency in the use of resources and biomass	5.1 Resource use efficiency, waste prevention and waste re-use along the whole bioeconomy value chain are improved	SDGs 6 & 13
		5.2 Food loss and waste is minimized and, when unavoidable, its biomass is reused or recycled	

Governance	6. Responsible and effective governance and mechanisms should underpin sustainable bioeconomy	<p>6.1 Policies, regulations and institutional structures relevant to bioeconomy sectors are adequately harmonized</p> <hr/> <p>6.2 Inclusive consultation processes and engagement of all relevant sectors of society are adequate and based on transparent sharing of information</p> <hr/> <p>6.3 Appropriate risk assessment and management, monitoring and accountability systems are put in place and implemented</p>	<p>SDG 16</p>
Economy	7. Sustainable bioeconomy should make good use of existing relevant knowledge and proven sound technologies and good practices and, where appropriate promote research and innovations.	<p>7.1 Existing knowledge is adequately valued and proven sound technologies are fostered</p> <hr/> <p>7.2 Knowledge generation and innovation are promoted</p>	<p>SDGs 4 & 9</p>
Economy	8. Sustainable bioeconomy should use and promote sustainable trade and market practices	8.1 Local economies are not constrained but rather expanded through the trade of raw and processed biomass, and related technologies	<p>SDG 10</p>
Society	9. Sustainable bioeconomy should address societal needs and encourage sustainable consumption	<p>9.1 Consumption patterns of bioeconomy goods match sustainable supply levels of biomass</p> <hr/> <p>9.2 Demand-side and supply-side market mechanisms and policy coherence between supply and demand of food and non-food goods are enhanced</p>	<p>SDG 12</p>
Governance	10. Sustainable bioeconomy should promote cooperation, collaboration and sharing between interested and concerned stakeholders in all relevant domains and at all relevant levels	10.1 Cooperation, collaboration and sharing of resources, skills and technologies are enhanced when and where appropriate	<p>SDG 17</p>

The European Commission has defined the bioeconomy as “the production of renewable biological resources and the conversion of these resources and waste streams into value added products, such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy” (COM, 2018, p. 4) with the blue bioeconomy referring to aquatic or marine environments, especially, with regards to novel aquaculture applications and non-food, food, and feed applications (COM 2019). In addition, the Commission specifies that the bioeconomy involves “all sectors and systems that rely on biological resources (animals, plants, micro-organisms and derived biomass, including organic waste), their functions and principles” (COM, 2018, p. 4) and that it connects land and marine ecosystems and their service provision. Besides, the primary production sectors, all other sectors, economic and industrial, which use and/or process biological resources to produce “food, feed, products, energy and services” are also considered as part of the bioeconomy (COM, 2018, p. 4).

There is ongoing work by the Commission also on bioeconomy indicators for the EU region which are further aligned with the EU’s bioeconomy goals (Giuntoli et al., 2021) but these were not available at the first phase of this project and so were not considered. Instead, the Commission’s Blue Economy indicator framework was reviewed and ultimately chosen for its thematic categories. The Commission’s Blue Economy Sustainability Framework (BESF) was based on a working definition of a sustainable blue economy which emphasizes all three pillars of sustainability and includes a variety of primary and secondary sectors similarly to the FAO framework. The full definition by the Commission was the following: “sustainable blue economy promotes economic growth, social inclusion and improved livelihoods while ensuring the environmental sustainability of the natural capital of the oceans and seas. For the purpose of this report, the sustainable blue economy encompasses all sectoral and cross-sectoral economic activities related to the oceans, seas and coasts. It comprises emerging sectors and economic value based on natural capital and non-market goods and services through the conservation of marine habitats and ecosystem services” (COM, 2021, p. 16). As with the FAO’s method, the report reviewed previous indicator frameworks in its selection and definition of indicators and included a sectoral approach although with an emphasis on blue sectors in particular. Critically assessed frameworks also included industry standards such as the MSC and ASC as well as international sustainability frameworks, such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Due to its focus on the blue economy, most of the frameworks that were selected for critical review were focused on maritime activities.

Ultimately, the Blue Economy Sustainability Framework (BESF) was comprised of the four main sustainability dimensions: economic, environmental, social and governance (see Table 2) and followed a value chain approach (COM, 2021). These four dimensions were also the sustainability dimensions in the FAO’s sustainable bioeconomy indicators’ framework (FAO, 2021) reflecting current trends in the delimitation of sustainability dimensions in the literature and in high level reports. Although sustainability has often been defined as depending on three pillars (economic, social, environmental) it has become increasingly accepted that governance must be included among them as a dimension that is crucial to the achievement of sustainability goals (Glass & Newig, 2019). This emphasis is also evident in the private sector’s Environment Social Governance (ESG) standards (Gillan, Koch & Starks, 2020).

The BESF dimensions and criteria listed in Table 2 comprise the core set of indicators applicable to all blue sectors. In addition to these, more sector-specific indicators (supplementary sets) were identified including the fisheries and aquaculture sectors (COM, 2021) which are the focus of this project.

Table 2 Criteria for the Blue Economy Sustainability Framework (adapted from COM, 2021).

Sustainability Dimension	Criteria
Environmental	Mitigation
	Emissions to air
	Impact on ecosystems
	Level of energy consumption
	Energy efficiency
	Waste/wastewater management
Economic	Concentration of businesses
	Economic benefits
	Economic viability
	Employment
	Financial viability
	Funding
	Costs
Social	Employment conditions
	Health and safety management
	Inclusiveness
	Fairness in remuneration
	Level of acceptance by stakeholders
Governance	Permits
	Impact assessment
	Nature-based solutions
	Risk management
	Strategy and vision
	Climate change
	Innovation
	Certification and labelling
	Supply chain
	Level of stakeholder engagement
	Education on sustainability

2. METHODS

The selection of indicators proceeded in a few basic steps (Figure 2). The first step was to agree internally on the main concepts that the project was targeting (circularity, sustainability in the blue bioeconomy) and build a common understanding of the project's scope and main goals. This was done in an iterative fashion as the scoping review of indicator frameworks resulted in two main frameworks which were then further discussed in internal meetings. The final choice of framework was then based on this common understanding of the project's scope and goals. The decision to look for pre-existing frameworks and indicator sets was taken to avoid duplication of efforts (Bracco et al., 2019). Both of the frameworks that were ultimately chosen were based on extensive review of other indicator sets and standards.

Once the framework had been agreed upon, a review of indicators within the selected framework (the Commission's Blue Economy Sustainability Framework) was conducted and further cross-referenced with the FAO's sustainable bioeconomy indicators (Bracco et al., 2019) which was considered to be more comprehensive but occasionally too detailed for the project's scope and aims. Next, further cross-referencing with the GRI reporting standards and company reports as an initial scoping of companies' current practices and data availability was conducted. The main criteria used for the final selection of indicators were a) relevance to the scope and aim and b) data availability. Finally, further internal meetings took place within the project's expert team to discuss the indicators' relevance as well as any outstanding issues (see Figure 2 below).

Figure 2 Process of indicator selection by expert team

3. RESULTS

The Blue Economy Sustainability Framework (BESF)'s sustainability dimensions and criteria were used to structure all the indicators. The criteria were compared to the FAO's sustainable bioeconomy criteria and where deemed necessary indicators were added to better capture the issue the criterion was targeting. This was in some cases necessary because the indicator was too general, or the measuring unit was not the best available one. The tables below (Tables 3-6) list all the selected indicators whereas the code column refers to where the indicator is sourced from. Codes beginning with C. EN; C.EC; C.SO and C. GO are from the BESF. The other indicators are sourced from the FAO 's Sustainable Bioeconomy framework and from the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) after cross-referencing with company reports.

The Comments column provides additional information where necessary. In some cases, a criterion was added; for example, in the Environmental dimension (Table 3) the criterion Green House Gas (GHG) emissions was added and the indicator measuring Scope 1, 2 and 3 emissions was added alongside it since it is becoming standard reporting practice for companies to report their direct and indirect GHG emissions in this accounting format. Similarly, Water Efficiency/Use and Water Quality (Table 3) were also added as it was deemed an oversight not to include these two relevant environmental issues in the BESF. The criterion of Transparency and Accountability (Table 6) was also added in the Governance dimension of the BESF as it is an important aspect of Governance for companies and sectors. The Comments column lists all the relevant additions and justifications for them. In some cases, indicators were rejected in favour of other ones; the rejected indicators are listed in Table 7 with the appropriate justification in the Comments column.

All in all, the final selection resulted in 35 indicators in the environmental dimension, 14 indicators in the economic dimension, 21 indicators in the social dimension and 20 indicators in the governance dimension (see tables 3-6). These comprise the core set. The supplementary sets, harvesting fish and shellfish, processing fish and shellfish and aquaculture include an additional 11 for harvesting, 22 for processing and 19 for aquaculture respectively (see tables 1-4 in Annex I).

Table 3 Selected indicators in the environmental dimension.

Environmental dimension				
Code	Criterion	Indicator	Unit	Comments
C.EN.1	MITIGATION	Gross value or percentage of revenue invested in environmental causes related to the sector’s activities directly (e.g., mitigation, restoration, monitoring) or indirectly (offsetting).	m EUR/year or % of revenue/year	The indicator is important in terms of tracking investments; however, mitigation, restoration and offsetting activities need to be based on third-party verified and accredited approaches and follow rigorous standards of social and environmental performance.
FAO		Life cycle GHG emissions	gr eq. CO2/product unit	The indicator provides a complete measurement of product GHG emissions based on standardized LCA approaches. An estimation of emissions over the entire life cycle of a product is necessary if companies are to avoid burden shifting.
FAO		Rate of GHG emissions reduction or savings	%	This indicator is useful for tracking progress but should be reported on an annual basis in direct comparison to both absolute GHG emissions, previous years’ performance, and an industry baseline where available.
GRI	GHG EMISSIONS	Direct and indirect GHG emissions	Scope 1 tCO2e/year	Scope 1, 2 and 3 emissions refer to all direct (1) and indirect emissions of GHG from company operations based on the most widely used GHG accounting standards, the GHG Protocol.
			Scope 2 tCO2e/year	
			Scope 3 tCO2e/year	
C.EN.2	EMISSIONS TO AIR	Emissions of CO2, SOx, NOx, and P.M.	Tonnes of CO2 equivalent / year	Absolute measurements of pollutants are important for assessing the scale of operations and should always complement indicators which measure rates of improvement. Tonnes of pollutant/year is a generic indicator for any significant pollutant from operations that has not been included in the set.
			Tonnes of SO2 equivalents / year	
			Tonnes of NO2 equivalents / year	

			Tonnes of pollutant / year	
GRI	IMPACT ON ECOSYSTEMS	Habitats protected or restored	Size, location, status and partnerships	GRI standards justification: This disclosure addresses the extent of an organization’s prevention and remediation activities with respect to its impacts on biodiversity. This disclosure refers to areas where remediation has been completed or where the area is actively protected. Areas where operations are still active can be counted if they conform to the definitions of ‘area restored’ or ‘area protected’. This indicator can be adapted to reflect the primarily marine-based operations of fisheries companies and still be able to account for habitat protection and restoration when it comes to aquaculture companies i.e., in terms of feed provision.
GRI		IUCN Red List species and national conservation list species with habitats in areas affected by operations	No. by level of extinction risk	The COM list included this indicator but in more general terms. The GRI standards stipulate that it is to be specific to areas affected by operations and that the measurement should also specify the level of extinction risk as is reported on the Red List. It also takes into account national conservation lists. The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red List of Threatened Species is an inventory which tracks global conservation status of plant and animal species. National conservation lists are based on the sensitivity of habitat in areas affected by operations, and on the relative importance of these habitats from a management perspective.
GRI		Significant impacts of activities, products, and services on biodiversity	Type of impact; area and species affected	GRI standards justification: “This disclosure provides the background for understanding (and developing) an organization’s strategy to mitigate significant direct and indirect impacts on biodiversity. By presenting structured and qualitative information, the disclosure enables comparison of the relative size, scale, and nature of impacts over time and across organizations.”
C.EN.5		Support given to local entities working on the protection,	% of turnover dedicated to such support or if in-kind support (such as	Many companies contribute to local conservation activities - financially or otherwise - this indicator provides an overview of such activities.

		conservation and management of local biodiversity and landscapes	making manpower or machinery available free of charge, or donating land), specify	
C.EN.6	LEVEL OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION	Energy consumption	Tonnes of oil equivalent (TOE) /year	These two indicators provide an overview of how much energy is consumed per year and how much of it is from renewable sources.
C.EN.7		Energy demand met by renewable energy	% total primary energy supply	
C.EN.8	ENERGY EFFICIENCY	Measures taken to increase energy efficiency	Yes / no. If yes, specify	Quantitative indicators of energy efficiency from the FAO set were added to this criterion to complement the qualitative overview of activities covered by indicator C.EN.8.
FAO		Primary energy savings	kWh or % of total primary energy consumed	
FAO		Energy Intensity	product value added / mJ primary energy	
FAO		Annual electricity consumption for manufactured products	kWh	
C.EN.9		Waste generated and recycled	Tonnes of waste generated and recycled/year	The criterion of “Waste/Wastewater Management” was split into two criteria: Waste management and Wastewater Management. Nine indicators from FAO set were added to the Waste Management criterion to provide a more comprehensive picture. Waste management is particularly relevant to circular bioeconomy issues.
FAO		Strategy for creating the infrastructure and systems necessary for recovering and recycling materials	yes/no	

FAO	WASTE MANAGEMENT	Presence of necessary infrastructure for safe burning of processing waste and by-products	yes/no	
FAO		Percentage of product is actively being recovered and recycled	%	Partially reported – tonnes of fish skin upcycled
FAO		Practices to segregate different waste types to facilitate reuse, recycling or composting (yes/no)	Yes/no	
FAO		Percentage of recycled materials for packaging	%	
FAO		Percentage of the sales packaging for your final products, by mass is biodegradable	%	
FAO		Percentage of the sales packaging for your final products, by mass, is recyclable	%	
FAO		Declaration of end-of-life disposal (in the CSR report) (yes/no)	Yes/no	
FAO		Number of innovative social projects that positively impacts reuse and recycle	No.	
FAO		Percentage of by-products or wastes reused by the processing/production facility or transferred to other sectors	%	
C.EN.9		Wastewater generated and reused	Million m ³ of wastewater generated and reused/year	Two indicators were added from the FAO set to add more detail on infrastructural elements needed for wastewater management.

C.EN.10	WASTEWATER MANAGMENT	Technology available for solid waste and wastewater treatment	Yes/ No. If yes: specify	(The same code (C.EN.9) is used twice for two different indicators as it is in the source material).
FAO	WATER QUALITY	Volume of water leaving the manufacturing facility meets drinking water quality standards	m3 or as % of total amount of water leaving the manufacturing facility	This FAO indicator was added to include the criterion on water quality which was not included in the COM set.
FAO	WATER USE/EFFICIENCY (FAO)	Water exploitation index	abstractions-returns)/renewable freshwater resources/product unit	Six indicators from the FAO set were added to water use and efficiency which was a criterion not included in the COM set.
FAO		Water consumption (use)	m3/product unit processed	
FAO		Water availability (m3/product unit)	% of reused and/or recycled wastewater	
FAO		Number of facility-wide water audit (amount of water used and opportunities to reduce the amount) is completed	No.	
FAO		Number and list of water-savings practices to increase the efficiency of the water use and reduce the amount of water used and/or wasted	No. and list	
FAO		Presence of a statement of water stewardship intentions describing actions being taken for mitigating identified problems and concerns is provided	Yes/no	

Table 4. Selected indicators in the economic dimension

Economic dimension				
Code	Criterion	Indicator	Unit	Comments
C.EC.1	CONCENTRATION OF BUSINESSES	Existence of clusters	Yes/No	The GRI indicator was included to provide a more balanced picture of the criterion.
GRI		Legal actions for anti-competitive behaviour, anti-trust, and monopoly practices	No.	
C.EC.2	ECONOMIC BENEFITS	Total revenues generated by local enterprises	% total revenues generated by local enterprises	Similarities with the GRI's reporting on the tax footprint.
C.EC.3		Local public revenue generated through time (taxes, fees, etc.)	m EUR/year	
C.EC.4	ECONOMIC VIABILITY	Gross value added (Size of the national/regional sector)	m EUR/year	
C.EC.5		Sector specific investments in the region	m EUR/year	
C.EC.6		Turnover	m EUR/year	
C.EC.7	EMPLOYMENT	Direct and indirect jobs	No. of direct and indirect jobs x1000 persons/year	
C.EC.8	FINANCIAL VIABILITY	Additional streams of finance/investment attracted	m EUR/year	
C.EC.9		Financial returns reinvested in local activities	% financial returns reinvested in local activities	
C.EC.10		Financial self-sustainability of supported activities	Number of years required to achieve the full financial self-sustainability of supported activities (e.g. debt-to-equity ratio)	
C.EC.11	FUNDING	Public/private funding	% of turnover	
C.EC.12	COSTS	Average personnel costs	x1000 EUR / year	
C.EC.13		Maintenance costs	Yes/ No. If yes: specify	

Table 5 Selected indicators in the social dimension

Social dimension				
Code	Criterion	Indicator	Unit	Comments
C.SO.1	EMPLOYMENT CONDITIONS	Average wage of employees compared to sector average or national average	EUR/year	
C.SO.2		Presence and activeness of labour unions in the company/sector	Yes/no. If yes, specify	
C.SO.3		Informal employment	% informal employment of total employment	
C.SO.4	HEALTH AND SAFETY MANAGEMENT	Frequency of auditing by external health & safety experts	No. of audits by external health and safety experts, including evidence of application in practice such as technical measures, regular medical screenings, etc. m EUR/year	Four indicators were added from the GRI standards: Two provide more quantitative assessment on workers' health and safety and the other two involve workers' representation.
C.SO.5		Existence of policies and measures to combat occupational diseases and accidents	Yes/no, if yes: specify	
GRI		Workers' representation in formal joint management worker health and safety committees	Yes/no	
GRI		Types of injury and rates of injury, occupational diseases, lost days, and absenteeism, and number of work-related fatalities	List and %	

GRI		Workers with high incidence or high risk of diseases related to their occupation	%	
GRI		Health and safety topics covered in formal agreements with trade unions	Yes/no	
C.SO.6	INCLUSIVENESS AND VULNERABILITY	Employees with no post-school diploma	% C.SO.7 Employment rate of vulnerable groups	Three indicators were added from the GRI to assess child and forced labour and discrimination at the workplace. The criterion was also renamed from Inclusiveness to Inclusiveness and Vulnerability to better reflect the issues covered by the indicators.
C.SO.7		Employment rate of vulnerable groups	% vulnerable workers of total work force per social category. For every social category define: Gender (% m/f/other) & average age	
GRI		Incidents of discrimination and corrective actions taken	No. and specify	
GRI		Operations and suppliers at significant risk for incidents of child labour	No.	
GRI		Operations and suppliers at significant risk for incidents of forced or compulsory labour	No.	
C.SO.8	FAIRNESS IN REMUNERATION	Evidence of unequal pay between social categories for equal work	Yes/no, if yes: explain evidence, type of work and social categories affected, degree of discrimination in pay	One indicator from the FAO was added to highlight gender equality as part of the fairness in remuneration criterion.
FAO		Rate of women having equal access to training and education and equal access to products and services as men	%	This indicator's unit was changed from a number to a rate.

C.SO.9	STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT AND ACCEPTANCE	Acceptance of environmental, economic and social impact by stakeholders	No. of reported actions of stakeholders against environmental, economic or social impacts	Four indicators from the GRI and FAO were added to this criterion to include stakeholder engagement activities which underpin stakeholder acceptance. The criterion was renamed Stakeholder engagement and acceptance to better reflect the content of the indicators.
FAO/ GRI		Number of effective participatory processes and participatory methodologies used to ensure meaningful stakeholder engagement	No.	
FAO		Number and variety of relevant stakeholders participating in the consultative process	No.	
FAO		Number of informal workshops to build local understanding in the community of the processes that may impact them directly to aid meaningful engagement	No.	
FAO		Promoting the involvement of small holders or small suppliers	Yes/no	

Table 6 Selected indicators in the governance dimension

Governance dimension				
Code	Criterion	Indicator	Unit	Comments
C.GO.1	PERMITS	Typical permitting regime followed prior to operations	Score: 1. No permitting or environmental administration required; 2. Permit procedure required, but below EIA threshold; 3. Permit with EIA procedure.	
C.GO.2	IMPACT ASSESSMENT	Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEnA) and Socio-Economic Assessment (SEcA) conducted and enforced via monitoring and evaluation	Score: 1. No EIA/SEnA/SEcA conducted, 2. EIA/SEnA/SEcA conducted but not implemented/enforced 3. EIA/SEnA/SEcA conducted and enforced via monitoring and evaluation	
C.GO.3	NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS	Application of Nature Based Solutions	Score 1. Relevant, but not applied 2. Applied to some extent [example] 3. Frequently applied [example] 4. Not applicable to the company/sector activities	
C.GO.5	STRATEGY AND VISION	Integration of SDGs in the company's strategy and operations	% of activities covered by SDG reporting	
C.GO.6	CLIMATE CHANGE	Measures taken for climate change adaptation	Yes/no. If yes: specify	

C.GO.7	INNOVATION	Attention to innovation (or investment in R&D)	% revenue invested in R&D	
C.GO.8	CERTIFICATION AND LABELLING	Existence of a sustainability label or certificate	Score: 1. No sustainability label or certification 2. Sustainability label(s) or certification exists/awarded (specify) 3. Sustainability label(s) or certification applied	
C.GO.9	SUPPLY CHAIN	Existence of supply chain policy	Yes/no. If yes: specify	
C.GO.10		Existence of Life Cycle Assessment policy	Yes/no. If yes: specify	
C.GO.12	EDUCATION ON SUSTAINABILITY	Participation in information and training sessions about sustainability	Yes/no, if yes specify	
C.GO.4	RISK ASSESSEMENT AND MANAGEMENT	Existence / implementation of risk management plans taking into account the precautionary principle	Score 1. No risk management plan 2. Risk management plan exists 3. Risk management plan exists, includes precautionary principles and is implemented	Four indicators from the FAO set were added to provide a more complete picture of risk assessment and management issues.
FAO		Presence of a system that ensures that all forms of bribery, conflicts of business interest and fraudulent practices are prohibited, including a written policy by the management and appropriate staff training	Yes/no	

FAO		Presence of a register containing all evidence of legal compliance (e.g. permits, licenses, evidence of lease, concessions, etc.) and a system ensuring that auxiliary conditions are met	Yes/no	
FAO		Presence of conflict management mechanisms	Yes/no	
FAO		Strength of organizational risk assessment with regard to potential for material resource conflict	Yes/no	
FAO	TRANSPARENCY AND ACCOUNTABILITY	Presence of a law or norm regarding transparency	Yes/no	
FAO		Non-compliance with regulations regarding transparency	Yes/no	
		Do internal management systems ensure that clear information is provided to consumers on end-of-life options	Yes/no	
FAO		Number of management documents publicly available, except where this is prevented by commercial confidentiality, of a proprietary nature or where disclosure of information would result in negative environmental or social outcomes	No.	
FAO		Presence of a legal register or equivalent system with all relevant applicable international, national and regional laws and regulations	Yes/no	

Table 7 List of rejected indicators and justification for rejection.

Rejected indicators				
Code	Criterion	Indicator	Unit	Comments
C.EN.3	IMPACT ON ECOSYSTEMS	Extent of coastal and marine habitat positively/negatively impacted	Area of positively and negatively impacted habitat in hectares.	Too generic. Impact is too vague a term for the indicator to be accurately measured. Instead, we propose several indicators from the GRI standards which provide more specific and measurable assessment. The supplementary sets also include some indicators that provide more targeted measurement of impact on ecosystems.
C.GO.11	LEVEL OF STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT	Mechanism for stakeholder engagement	Score 1. No stakeholder involvement 2. Occasional consultation with stakeholders, focused on public actors 3. Specific mechanism for stakeholder engagement besides public actors	Rejected because the addition of several indicators in the stakeholder acceptance and engagement criterion in the social dimension make this indicator and criterion redundant.
SAQ.EN.1	CHEMICAL USE	On-farm documentation available with detailed information on chemicals use, compliant with regulations (including antibiotics)	Yes/no. If yes: specify	Precise indicators from the Global Salmon Initiative were added in the supplementary aquaculture set for more accurate measurement of critical variables making this indicator redundant.
SAQ.EN.3	FARM MANAGEMENT	Mortalities reduction program exists and implemented	Yes/no. If yes: specify	Rejected in favour of a more quantitative indicator from the GSI.
SFP.GO.1	SUPPLY CHAIN	Existence and effective implementation of a company policy to ensure inputs/raw materials are obtained from sustainable sources	Score 1. Policy does not exist 2. Policy exists but not implemented 3. Policy exists and implemented	Rejected in favour of more quantitative indicators from the GRI standards.

4. CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEPS

The indicators were selected for sustainability assessment of circular business models in the blue bioeconomy systems and for assessing performance against sustainability criteria including environmental, economic social and governance aspects. An assessment of synergies and trade-offs among the different sustainability dimensions can be conducted through stakeholder-based weighing procedures and trade-off/synergy analysis.

The next step would be to define targets based on national-level policy targets (more common) or sectoral level targets (where available) and to use trend-based assessment where those targets are missing. Further discussion at the project level is also necessary to define those indicators most specific to the aims of other WPs. Ongoing work includes interviews covering the sustainability dimensions and probing further on circularity and governance more broadly.

LIMITATIONS

One major issue with indicator sets is that they tend to be quite demanding in terms of the amount of data that needs to be collected. However, the demand for more detailed data is not likely to reduce in the coming years. Increasingly sophisticated reporting standards such as the GRI and ESG standards, as well as regulation such as the EU directive on non-financial disclosures and the EU taxonomy show that regulators and investors are increasingly more interested in the sustainability aspects of business (KPMG 2020; Stolowy & Paugam, 2018). Another case in point is the data required by Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) whose 231 unique indicators dwarf the 60 indicators by which the previous global Goals (the Millennium Development Goals) were to be measured (Kitzmueller, Stacy & Mahler, 2021). The advantage of using previously developed indicator sets such the main two that were used here is that extensive review work that was put into their development ensures that the indicators chosen are for the most part already being used in some capacity and that the methodology behind them is well-defined.

Second, the focus on the blue bioeconomy is important because marine activities for example in relation to food production have received less research and policy attention. However, this focus also represents a limitation because circularity demands also that attention be paid to the connection of marine systems to terrestrial systems. This lack of focus on land-sea interactions is not trivial but is beyond the scope of this project.

Finally, a top-down, expert-led approach of indicator selection would need to be complemented by a bottom-up, stakeholder-led approach (Bracco et al., 2019). In-depth interviews with stakeholders in the fisheries and aquaculture sectors of Iceland and Norway are currently under-way.

NEXT STEPS

The SMARTCHAIN project's scope is the blue bioeconomy: aquatic or marine environments, and involves a specific focus on novel applications, including non-food, food, and feed. The blue bioeconomy includes both primary and secondary activities and other sectors may be connected to the blue bioeconomy through their services to bioeconomic activities. The next steps include exploring the perceptions of companies, experts and policy makers in Iceland and Norway to gauge the ways in which they contribute to the circular bioeconomy. The main goal is to elucidate the opportunities and challenges for further advancement of circular blue bioeconomy activities and strategies.

5. REFERENCES

- Böhringer, C., & Jochem, P.E.P. (2007). Measuring the immeasurable - A survey of sustainability indices. *Ecological Economics*, 63(1): 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2007.03.008>
- Bracco, S., Tani, A., Çalicioğlu, Ö., Gomez San Juan, M., & Bogdanski, A. (2019). *Indicators to monitor and evaluate the sustainability of bioeconomy. Overview and a proposed way forward*. Rome, FAO. Retrieved from: <https://www.fao.org/3/ca6048en/ca6048en.pdf>
- Carus, M., & Dammer, L. (2018). *The “Circular Bioeconomy” – Concepts, Opportunities and Limitations*, Hürth 2018-01. Accessed at: www.bio-based.eu/nova-papers
- COM (2018). *A sustainable bioeconomy for Europe: strengthening the connection between economy, society, and the environment: updated bioeconomy strategy*. Publications Office. Retrieved from: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/792130>
- COM (2019). *Blue Bioeconomy Forum: Roadmap for the blue bioeconomy*. Retrieved from: <https://op.europa.eu/s/w26i>
- COM (2021). *Sustainability criteria for the blue economy*. European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). doi: 10.2826/399476
- FAO (2021). *Aspirational principles and criteria for a sustainable bioeconomy*. Rome. Retrieved from: <https://www.fao.org/3/cb3706en/cb3706en.pdf>
- Fritsche et al., (2020). *Future transitions for the Bioeconomy towards sustainable development and a climate-neutral economy - Knowledge synthesis final report*. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.
- Gillan, S. L., Koch, A., & Starks, L. T. (2021). Firms and social responsibility: A review of ESG and CSR research in corporate finance. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 66, 101889. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2021.101889>.
- Glass, L. M., & Newig, J. (2019). Governance for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals: How important are participation, policy coherence, reflexivity, adaptation and democratic institutions? *Earth System Governance*, 2, 100031. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esg.2019.100031>.
- Giuntoli, J., Robert, N., Ronzon, T., Sanchez Lopez, J., Follador, M., Girardi, I., Barredo Cano, J., Borzacchiello, M., Sala, S., M'Barek, R., La Notte, A., Becker, W., & Mubareka, S. (2020). *Building a monitoring system for the EU bioeconomy*, EUR 30064 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, ISBN 978-92-76-15385-6, doi:10.2760/717782, JRC119056.
- Hák, T., Moldan, B., & Dahl, A. L. (2007). *Sustainability Indicators: A scientific assessment*. SCOPE publication series. Island Press.
- Kitzmueller, L., Stacy, B., & Mahler, D. G. (2021). *Are we there yet? Many countries don't report progress on all SDGs according to the World Bank's new Statistical Performance Indicators*. Accessed September 6, 2021 at <https://blogs.worldbank.org/opendata/are-we-there-yet-many-countries-dont-report-progress-all-sdgs-according-world-banks-new>
- KPMG (2020). *The time has come: The KPMG Survey of Sustainability Reporting 2020*. Retrieved from: <https://assets.kpmg/content/dam/kpmg/xx/pdf/2020/11/the-time-has-come.pdf>
- Nordic Council (2014). *Future Opportunities for Bioeconomy in the West Nordic Countries*. Available at: <http://norden.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:791350/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- Pieroni et al., (2019). Business model innovation for circular economy and sustainability: A review of approaches. *Journal of cleaner production*, 215, 198-216
- Ruffing, K. (2007). *Indicators to measure decoupling of environmental pressure from economic growth*. In T. Hák, B. Moldan & A. L. Dahl (2007). *Sustainability Indicators: A scientific assessment* (pp. 211-222). SCOPE publication series. Island Press.
- Stolowy, H., & Paugam, L. (2018). The expansion of non-financial reporting: an exploratory study. *Accounting and Business Research*, 48(5), 525-548, DOI: 10.1080/00014788.2018.1470141

Vadén, T., Lähde, V., Majava, A., Järvensivu, P., Toivanen, T., Hakala, E., & Eronen, G. T. (2020). Decoupling for ecological sustainability: A categorisation and review of research literature. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 112, 236-244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2020.06.016>.

ANNEX I

SUPPLEMENTARY INDICATOR SETS

Table 1. Supplementary indicator set for the harvesting of fish and shellfish

SUPPLEMENTARY SET: HARVESTING FISH AND SHELLFISH				
Code	Criterion	Indicator	Unit	Comments
ENVIRONMENTAL				
SFH.EN.1	STATUS OF STOCK	Exploitation of stock at Maximum Sustainable Yield	% stock exploited at Maximum Sustainable Yield (per species)	
SFH.EN.2	FISHERY MANAGEMENT	Use of selective fishing techniques/gears	Yes/no. If no, specify	
SFH.EN.3		Use of non-destructive fishing techniques/gears	Yes/no. If no, specify	
ECONOMICS				
SFH.EC.1	ECONOMIC VIABILITY	Production ' harvested fish and shellfish' (monetary)	m EUR/year	
SFH.EC.2		Production ' harvested fish and shellfish' (weight)	Landings weight in tons/year	
SOCIAL				
SFP.SO.1	SOCIAL BALANCE	Effect of fish input purchases on: • local prices • local harvesters • users of fish	Yes/no, if yes specify for each category	
GOVERNANCE				
SFH.GO.1	FISHERY MANAGEMENT	Multiannual management plans in place and implemented	Yes/no. If yes specify	
SFH.GO.2		National Plan of Action for Illegal, Unregulated, Unreported Landings	Yes/no. If yes specify	
SFH.GO.3		Quota system in place and implemented	Yes/no, if yes specify	
SFH.GO.4		Fishing vessels equipped with electronic positioning and catch reporting device	% of the unit of analysis	

SFP.GO.1	SUPPLY CHAIN	Existence and effective implementation of a company policy to ensure inputs/raw materials are obtained from sustainable sources	Score 1. Policy does not exist 2. Policy exists but not implemented 3. Policy exists and implemented	
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Table 2. Supplementary indicator set for the processing of fish and shellfish

SUPPLEMENTARY SET: PROCESSING FISH AND SHELLFISH				
Code	Criterion	Indicator	Unit	Comments
ENVIRONMENTAL				
SFP.EN.2	WASTE/WASTEWATER MANAGEMENT	Use of recycled packaging materials	Yes/no. If no, specify	Four indicators for the FAO set were added to the criterion of “Waste/Wastewater Management” to provide a more comprehensive picture. Waste and wastewater management are particularly relevant to circular bioeconomy issues.
SFP.EN.1		Treatment of wastewater	Yes/no. If no, specify	
SFP.EN.3		Re-use of fish waste	Yes/no. If no, specify	
FAO		Amount of wastewater from processing operations is discharged into aquatic systems	m ³	
FAO		Amount of sewage is discharged into aquatic systems	m ³	
FAO		Percentage of wastewater containing potential organic and mineral contaminants are treated or recycled to prevent negative impacts	%	
FAO		Percentage of chemical waste and empty containers is collected and disposed in compliance with good practices	%	
FAO	ENERGY EFFICIENCY/USE	Number of energy-efficient infrastructure for drying and processing biomass	No.	The criterion of “Energy Efficiency” was added along with three indicators from the FAO set.
FAO		Fuel consumption for cultivation and drying of biomass	l/biomass unit	
FAO		Energy consumption for cultivation and drying of biomass	kWh	
ECONOMIC				
SFP.EC.1		Production 'processed fish and shellfish' (monetary)	m EUR/year	

SFP.EC.2	ECONOMIC VIABILITY	Production 'processed fish and shellfish' (weight)	Tons/year	One indicator from the GRI standards was added to provide more detail on processing operations.
SFP.EC.4		Domestic fish production vs. imports	Tons/year	
SFP.EC.5		Type of imports	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tons/year for the following categories: • (Frozen) whole fish • (Frozen) fillet and steaks • Canned fish and shellfish • Dried (frozen) fish • Fresh fish and shellfish 	
GRI		Percentage and total of animals raised and/or processed, by species and breed type	%	
SFP.EC.3		PROCESSING CONDITIONS	Access to ice / refrigeration	
SOCIAL				
SFP.SO.1	SOCIAL BALANCE	Effect of fish input purchases on: • local prices • local harvesters • users of fish	Yes/no, if yes specify for each category	
GOVERNANCE				
GRI	SOURCING POLICIES	Percentage of purchased volume from suppliers compliant with company's sourcing policy	%	Two indicators were added from the GRI standards to the criterion of "Sourcing policies" which replacing the criterion "Supply Chain" and one indicator from the COM framework.
GRI		Percentage of purchased volume, which is verified as being in accordance with credible, internationally recognized responsible production standards, broken down by standard	%	
GRI	FOOD SAFETY	Percentage of production volume manufactured in sites certified by an independent third party according to internationally recognized food safety management system standards	%	The criterion of food safety was added along with one indicator from the GRI standards.
GRI	NUTRITION	Percentage of total sales volume of consumer products, by product category, that are lowered in saturated fat, trans fats, sodium and added sugars	%	The criterion of nutrition was added from the GRI standards along with two indicators.
GRI		Percentage of total sales volume of consumer products, by product category, that contain increased nutritious ingredients like fibre, vitamins, minerals, phytochemicals or functional food additives	%	

Table 3. Supplementary indicator set for aquaculture.

SUPPLEMENTARY SET: AQUACULTURE				
Code	Criterion	Indicator	Unit	Comments
Environmental dimension				
GSI	CHEMICAL USE	Antibiotics used	g API/tonne of LWE	The indicator for this criterion was too generic so it was rejected in favour of two indicators from the GSI which require more precise measurement. According to the GSI, the amount of antibiotics used is calculated as the amount of active pharmaceutical ingredients (API) used (in g) per tonne of fish produced (LWE).
GSI		Sea lice treatments	g API/tonne of LWE via bath and via feed	The amount of treatment used is calculated as the amount of active pharmaceutical ingredients (API) used (in grams) per tonne of fish produced (LWE).
GSI	SOURCING POLICIES	Share of deforestation-free soy protein concentrate from Brazil with traceability	%	
GSI	FARM MANAGEMENT	Fish mortality	12 month rolling mortality rate	12 months rolling mortality calculated based on the Global Salmon Initiative’s methodology.
SAQ.EN.4		Number of escape events	No. of escapes / year	
SAQ.EN.5		Number of escaped fish	No. of escaped fish / year	
SAQ.EN.6	WATER QUALITY	Measures taken to reduce nutrient eutrophication	No. and type of measures taken	
SAQ.EN.7		Phosphorous (P) and nitrogen (N) concentrations	mg/L	
SAQ.EN.8	IMPACT ON ECOSYSTEMS	Refuge effect for species	Yes/no, if yes: specify	
L-KPI		Average fallow period	Average number of days	
GSI		Wildlife interactions and accidental mortalities	Total number of interactions/total number of sites from January to December each year.	Accidental mortalities: birds and mammals.
SAQ.EC.1		Average size of farms	Hectares of land or water	

SAQ.EC.2	ECONOMIC VIABILITY	Production ‘farmed fish’ (weight)	Tons/year	
SAQ.EC.3		Production ‘farmed fish’ (monetary)	m EUR/year	
SAQ.EC.5		Stocking density	No. of fry / m2	
SAQ.EC.4	FEED MANAGEMENT	Realised Feed Conversion Ratio	Feed Conversion Ratio	
GSI	FISH HEALTH AND WELFARE	Average density per cage at sea	kg/m3	The criterion of “Fish Health and Welfare” was added along with three indicators from the GSI.
GSI		Survival in sea	%	12 months rolling mortality calculated based on the Global Salmon Initiative’s methodology
GSI		Average number of fully grown lice per fish in LSG Farming	Average no.	

Table 4. Rejected indicators from the supplementary sets with justification.

Rejected indicators				
Code	Criterion	Indicator	Unit	Comments
C.EN.3	IMPACT ON ECOSYSTEMS	Extent of coastal and marine habitat positively/negatively impacted	Area of positively and negatively impacted habitat in hectares.	Too generic. Impact is too vague a term for the indicator to be accurately measured. Instead, we propose several indicators from the GRI standards which provide more specific and measurable assessment. The supplementary sets also include some indicators that provide more targeted measurement of impact on ecosystems.
C.GO.11	LEVEL OF STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT	Mechanism for stakeholder engagement	Score 1. No stakeholder involvement 2. Occasional consultation with stakeholders, focused on public actors 3. Specific mechanism for stakeholder engagement besides public actors	Rejected because the addition of several indicators in the stakeholder acceptance and engagement criterion in the social dimension make this indicator and criterion redundant.

SAQ.EN.1	CHEMICAL USE	On-farm documentation available with detailed information on chemicals use, compliant with regulations (including antibiotics)	Yes/no. If yes: specify	Precise indicators from the Global Salmon Initiative were added in the supplementary aquaculture set for more accurate measurement of critical variables making this indicator redundant.
SAQ.EN.3	FARM MANAGEMENT	Mortalities reduction program exists and implemented	Yes/no. If yes: specify	Rejected in favour of a more quantitative indicator from the GSI.
SFP.GO.1	SUPPLY CHAIN	Existence and effective implementation of a company policy to ensure inputs/raw materials are obtained from sustainable sources	Score 1. Policy does not exist 2. Policy exists but not implemented 3. Policy exists and implemented	Rejected in favour of more quantitative indicators from the GRI standards.